

AI IN LEARNING LANGUAGES

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Abstract: in this thesis, it is explored the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into the language learning process. The purpose from this thesis is the analysis of how AI-based tools can help to improve learning languages. AI-powered applications such as Elsa Speak, ChatGPT and Duolingo are reviewed in methodologies. Results from the researches show that using AI-based applications are more useful and effective in language learning processes, especially, grammar, pronunciation and vocabulary than the traditional methods. As a conclusion, it is recorded AI-based tools are much more effective and potential in language learning process.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, language learning, AI-based tool, AI-powered applications, Duolingo, ChatGPT, pronunciation.

Аннотация: В данной выпускной работе рассматривается интеграция искусственного интеллекта (ИИ) в процесс изучения языков. Целью исследования является анализ того, как ИИ-инструменты могут способствовать улучшению процесса изучения языков. В разделе методологии рассматриваются ИИ-приложения, такие как Elsa Speak, ChatGPT и Duolingo. Результаты исследований показывают, что использование ИИ-приложений оказывается более полезным и эффективным в процессе изучения языков, особенно в таких аспектах, как грамматика, произношение и словарный запас, по сравнению с традиционными методами. В заключение отмечается, что ИИ-инструменты обладают значительно большей эффективностью и потенциалом в процессе изучения языков.

Ключевые слова: искусственный интеллект, изучение языков, ИИ-инструмент, ИИ-приложения, Duolingo, ChatGPT, произношение.

Learning a foreign language is crucial in today's world. People may learn languages for different reasons like travelling, working or studying abroad and catching up with new technologies. Because modern technologies, particularly, artificial intelligence (AI) has considerably changed the way of language learning process in a positive manner. The main purpose of this thesis is to determine the role of AI-based methods in language learning, to evaluate the efficiency of them and to offer as a practical method.

In these days, AI-powered applications such as Duolingo, Babel, Elsa speak are being used commonly in language learning processes. These

applications can help to give exercises according to their degree of learning, to listen to the speech and analyse pronunciation and to try to create a real conversation atmosphere. Chatbots like ChatGPT can help to improve speaking skills by creating a good atmosphere for conversation.

In this thesis, comparison is used among quality analysis, users' experience and practical methods. Students who used AI-powered applications constantly showed much better results in terms of memorizing vocabulary, understanding grammar and improving pronunciation than ones who learned the language by using traditional methods. Besides, these tools give us the opportunity to use everywhere and anytime and offer adapted exercises to every student.

In this method it is new that there are new and modern ways of learning languages which are not implemented in traditional ways. AI can be effective not only in self-study but also in traditional classes. It should not disturb teachers but help to teach and ensure individual approach.

To conclude, AI- based tools make the language learning process more effective, interactive and directed to students. Research results show that it is possible to improve the degree of students in language learning by applying AI-based methods. It is clear that in the future artificial intelligence (AI) will be more modernised and developed and affect the quality of education system positively.

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